

Special Relativity Energy-Momentum Relation in terms of Projections

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Special relativity is often described in terms of a Lorentz transformation. Historically Lorentz considered Maxwell's electromagnetic equations viewed from a moving frame. Einstein considered motion in a moving frame using light as a measuring device with the assumption that the speed of light is the same in all frames and cannot be surpassed.

In this note we try to think of a single equation describing E and p , but with the ability to describe two different objects, namely a particle with rest mass and a photon. The photon is known to have the dispersion relationship $E=pc$ while one may postulate $p=E(v)/v$ for a particle with rest mass i.e. a usual flux equation. At first these seem very different, but if one considers Ev/c with c being the largest velocity attainable (as Einstein assumed) then v/c maps into $\sin(\theta)$ i.e. it is a projection. If $v \rightarrow c$ then $E \rightarrow E$ which is the photon result so there can be no extra component. What is the extra component for $v < c$? It should be $E \cos(\theta)$, but if $\theta = 0$ then $Ev/c = 0$ (i.e. $v \rightarrow 0$) and this extra component is proportional to rest mass m_0 . $\cos(\theta) \cos(\theta) = (1 - v^2/c^2)$ so $E \cos(\theta) = m_0 c^2$. This seems to be an alternative approach to obtaining the $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ relationship. It is possible that such an argument has been suggested before in the literature, but it does not seem to be the standard approach used in describing special relativity.

Special Relativity In Terms of Two Objects with Differing Dispersion Relationships

Newtonian mechanics has long dealt with objects with a rest mass and defines momentum p as mv where m_0 is mass. There is no difference in rest mass or moving mass nonrelativistically and v , velocity, may take on any value. Light on the other hand is known from Young's experiment to exhibit wave properties and was later found by Maxwell to be a solution to his electromagnetic equations without sources. As a result there seem to be two very different objects which both have energy and momentum. For example, experimentally it is found that photons create impulses when striking foil. These objects have different dispersion relationships as the nonrelativistic rest mass particle follows $p = m_0 v$ and light $E = pc$.

Assume that one wishes to have an equation in E and p (and possibly other variables like m_0) which describes either a particle with rest mass and a photon. The reason for one equation is that "energy is energy" and "momentum is momentum". A foil struck by the same momentum carried by a photon or a particle with rest mass recoils in the same way. The problem which immediately arises is the differing dispersion relationships:

$$((1a)) \quad p = E(v)/v \quad \text{particle with rest mass} \quad ((1b)) \quad E = pc \quad \text{light}$$

Here we generalize $p = mv$ and assume that E changes with v . At first these appear to be completely unconnected, but if one assumes that c is the maximum speed which a rest mass particle may attain (as Einstein assumed) then:

$E v/c$ is a projection i.e. $E v/c = E \sin(\theta)$ ((2))

For light $v=c$ and so there is only one dimension i.e. $E=pc$. For a particle with rest mass, if $v=0$ there is still rest mass which represents energy. Thus:

$$E^2 = E^2 v^2/c^2 + E^2 (1-v^2/c^2) \quad ((3))$$

The second term $E^2 (1-v^2/c^2)$ must be proportional to m_0 because it disappears for a photon i.e. $m_0 \rightarrow 0$. For $v=0$, E is proportional to m_0 so a solution is:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((4))$$

This ensures that the rest mass component does not disappear as $v \rightarrow c$.

Thus we argue that one may develop the energy-momentum relationship:

$$E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((5))$$

by the above argument which does not seem to be a standard way of describing special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, special relativity is usually considered within its historical context and linked to a Lorentz transformation which is extremely useful. Here we investigate whether one may obtain the energy-momentum relationship $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m_0^2 c^4$ by different arguments. We suggest that one equation in E and p should describe either the photon or a particle with rest mass because energy and momentum should not depend on the type of object in question (in the equation). These two objects seem to be completely different with different dispersion relationships i.e. $E=pc$ for light and we suggest $p=E(v)/v$ for a particle with rest mass. In order to link the two objects we use Einstein's assumption that c is the largest velocity attainable by a particle with rest mass. Then v/c maps into $\sin(\theta)$. For the photon $v=c$ so $\sin(\theta=90 \text{ deg})$ is the only solution i.e. there is one projection. For a particle with rest mass there are two projections i.e.

$E^2 = E^2 v^2/c^2 + E^2 (1-v^2/c^2)$. For $v \rightarrow 0$ E should be proportional to m_0 . For all v E should be proportional to m_0 because this term must vanish for a photon i.e. $m_0 \rightarrow 0$. If $v \rightarrow c$ the second term should not disappear so one may suggest $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ as a solution.